

Determination of evacuation routes and shelter sites in a coastal-settlements during forest fire disasters using GIS

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Summary

Lately, there has been an increase in forest fires in many different parts of the world. Therefore, it is essential outlining evacuation routes and shelters against possible fire disasters. In this study, network analysis was used to prepare the evacuation plans of the settlements close to the fire area. Location-allocation and closest facility analysis were done using walking time and distance parameters to access and determine secure and shelter fields. In line with the results obtained, it is thought that specific evacuation methods should be advanced for the places where the distance and time to the shelter locations are longer.

KEYWORDS: Forest fire, shelter area, evacuation route, network analysis

1. Introduction

Following the 2019 – 2020 Australian forest fires, millions of hectares of forest were affected by the fires that arose in Europe, the USA, Russia, Mexico, Canada, and the Middle East in 2021. Only in Turkey, the total burned area was reached 204,408 hectares (EFFIS, 2021). In this study, the determination of evacuation routes and shelter sites during forest fires were researched with GIS network analysis. In previous studies, different methods have been investigated in determining evacuation routes and shelter areas for various natural disaster scenarios such as earthquakes, floods, and tsunamis. Zhao et al. (2017) implemented the location-allocation model for emergency shelter planning in Shanghai. Trenggana (2018) identified temporary and final evacuation locations and evacuation routes during the Cold Lava Flood using network analysis techniques. In tsunami disaster studies, applying different periods for workers and tourists (Trindade et al., 2018), mapping temporary evacuation areas (Putra & Mutmainah, 2016) and determining emergency evacuation areas for buildings (Bonilauri et al., 2021) were investigated.

In the summer of 2021, forest fires occurred in many different parts of Muğla. Seeing as people run away without knowing what to do during fires has revealed that a solution should be found in this regard. Therefore, in the study it was prioritized to evacuate the people during a fire in coastal settlements and ensure access to safe shelter areas and the ports.

Accordingly, location-allocation and closest facility analysis were used to access security zones. The location-allocation method aimed to determine adequate and suitable coverage of shelter zones. Subsequently, the most secure access options from shelter fields to the ports were decided on with the closest facility analysis, based on walking distance and time parameters.

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2. Description of Study Area and Materials

The research area was selected as a coastal settlement Marmaris, which is %80 forestland of the total area. Marmaris is one of the districts of Muğla province and is located between 36°50'54.64" N and 28°16'10.05" E coordinates (Figure 1). The study area consists of 9 neighbourhoods and is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Neighbourhoods of Study Area

Neighbourhood	Area (km ²)	Population
Armutalan	1.091	22.805
Beldibi	1.439	11.139
Çamdibi	0.827	3.709
Çıldır	0.580	6.749
Hatipirimi	0.441	3.800
Kemeraltı	0.649	6.909
Sarıana	0.368	4.562
Siteler	0.711	2.866
Tepe	0.400	6.978

Figure 1. Study Area

The building data that can be appointed as a shelter was downloaded from OpenStreetMap. In total, there are 2073 buildings in the study area, and 16 appropriate public buildings that might be used as shelter are given in Table 2.

Table 2 Possible Shelter Buildings

Public Building Type	Number of Buildings
Schools	5
Mosques	7
Health Centers	1
Neighbourhood Unit	1
Police Office	1
Culture and Art Center	1

GIS data of neighbourhoods and seaports of Marmaris District was obtained from the Başarsoft Information Technologies Co. The dataset visualization of study area is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Visualization of Dataset

3. Methodology

Two different network analysis algorithms were used to determine evacuation routes and shelter places. First, the location-allocation method between the shelters and the buildings, that need to be evacuated, was implemented. Afterwards, a secure and closest path from the shelters to the ports was resolved. The flowchart of the work model is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Flow Chart

3.1. Location- Allocation Method

The first method of this study is Minimize Impedance (p - median) Method which is one of the location-allocation algorithms. P -median problem is one of the location selection problems, which aims to find the location of p facilities using n nodes in a network in a way that minimizes the total average weighted distance between demand and facility (Durak & Yildiz, 2015). P -median problems are often used in site selection studies given in the equation.

$$\text{Minimize} = \sum_i \sum_j a_i d_{ij} x_{ij}$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i,$$

$$x_{ij} \leq x_{jj} \quad \forall i, j,$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{jj} = p,$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall i, j,$$

where $x_{ij} = 1$ if demand i is assigned to a facility j , $x_{ij} = 0$ otherwise, n is the number of demand points, a_i is the population of demand i , d_{ij} the shortest distance between i and j , p is the number of facility points to be located (Rahman & Smith, 2000). In this study, facilities are shelter areas while demand points are buildings which should be evacuated (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Location-Allocation

According to the location-allocation results, the minimum walking time from the buildings to the shelters is 8 seconds, while the maximum walking time is calculated as 31 minutes and 20 seconds.

3.2. Closest Facility Method

Secondly, the closest paths between the incidents and the facilities were resolved with the closest facility method. The closest paths from the shelters to the seaports is shown in Figure 5. According to the closest facility results, the minimum time from the shelters to the seaports is 4 minutes 22 seconds, and the maximum time is computed as 55 minutes 35 seconds.

Figure 5. Closest paths from the shelters to the seaports

4. Conclusions

It is very important for the people to appoint the shelters in advance for possible disaster situations. Previous studies have dealt with tsunami, flood or earthquake disasters, and the evacuation areas have been developed as emergency shelters. Unlike the others, shelters were allocated from public buildings, and the two parameters, walking time and distance, were used together in the computations, in this study. Specific evacuation methods should be advanced for the places where the distance and time to the shelter locations are longer.

5. Acknowledgements

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References

- Bonilauri, E. M., Harris, A. J. L., Morin, J., Ripepe, M., Mangione, D., Lacanna, G., Ciolli, S., Cusolito, M., & Deguy, P. (2021). Tsunami evacuation times and routes to safe zones: a GIS-based approach to tsunami evacuation planning on the island of Stromboli, Italy. *Journal of Applied Volcanology*, 10(1), 1–19.
- Durak, İ., & Yıldız, M. S. (2015). P-Medyan Tesis Yeri Seçim Problemi: Bir Uygulama. *Journal of Alanya Faculty of Business/Alanya Isletme Fakültesi Dergisi*, 7(2).
- EFFIS (European Forest Fire Information System), 2021. EFFIS Annual Country Statistics for TR – Turkey, retrieved from <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/apps/effis.statistics/effisestimates>, access date: 12/01/2022.
- Putra, A., & Mutmainah, H. (2016). The Mapping of Temporary Evacuation Site (TES) and Tsunami Evacuation Route in North Pagai Island, Mentawai Islands Regency - Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 47(1).
- Rahman, S. U., & Smith, D. K. (2000). Use of location-allocation models in health service development planning in developing nations. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 123(3), 437-452.
- Trenggana, S. (2018). Spatial Modeling of Cold Lava Flood Evacuation in Kali Putih, Magelang Regency, Using Network Analyst. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology*, 3(4), 1499–1517.
- Trindade, A., Teves-Costa, P., & Catita, C. (2018). A GIS-based analysis of constraints on pedestrian tsunami evacuation routes: Cascais case study (Portugal). *Natural Hazards*, 93(s1), 169–185.
- Zhao, L.; Li, H.; Sun, Y.; Huang, R.; Hu, Q.; Wang, J.; Gao, F. Planning Emergency Shelters for Urban Disaster Resilience: An Integrated Location-Allocation Modeling Approach. *Sustainability* 2017, 9, 2098.

Biographies

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